

Burns from foul play? No – previously unsuspected epilepsy

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SUMMARY

Introduction. Injuries such as burns may occur from unwitnessed and unsuspected new onset epilepsy with forensic implications.

Case report. A young woman was found with >25% 2nd and 3rd degree body burns after an unwitnessed morning event in a shower.

Discussion. The onset of tonic-clonic seizures and limb jerks in adolescence with a typical EEG recording of 3–4/second spike/polyspike-and-waves are diagnostic of Juvenile Myoclonic Epilepsy (JME). Worldwide there is a significant morbidity and mortality in epilepsy from burns. The treatment of JME and of burns was discussed.

Key words: JME • tonic-clonic seizure • burns

INTRODUCTION

Unsuspected epilepsy can occasionally present with injury following a seizure. On such occasions, the seizure itself may not have been witnessed. This may lead to “mysterious” injury or death from unheralded and unsuspected epilepsy onset. The forensic aspect is resolved when an EEG shows classic patterns of genetic epilepsy or when further seizures supervene.

CASE REPORT

A 17-year-old woman was found scalded with 26% total body surface second and third degree burns on the dependent parts of the back, neck and scalp. She had been lying in a shower with the hot water on, and her fall had not been heard. She had been up late the night before, and relatives suspected foul play for unclear reasons. Her mother remembers staring spells as a child, occasional limb jerks in the morning and some febrile seizures, but no diagnosis was made.

In the Burns-ICU she received skin-grafts, acute management of electrolytes and infection, and re-

mained sedated and unable to provide a history. Eighteen days into her stay there was a witnessed tonic-clonic seizure. Neurological examination was without focality in a mildly sedated patient. Head CT was normal and EEG revealed the typical generalized runs of spike-wave discharges at 3 to 4 Hz, lasting up to 10 seconds. She was treated with valproate, then lamotrigine and finally with levetiracetam with sporadic seizures over the next three years.

DISCUSSION

The clinical history of staring spells, occasional limb jerks and a tonic-clonic seizure with generalized spike waves are diagnostic of Juvenile Myoclonic Epilepsy (Kaplan et al., 2002). This common childhood epilepsy may not be diagnosed for many years after the appearance of morning jerks and childhood staring spells, until a convulsion brings appropriate attention and investigation. Absence seizures usually appear in early childhood, while jerks occurring several years later are

Some of these risks are avoidable since insulated kettles and hot-water bottles are available. A companion in the kitchen or switching roles may help avoid cooking burns, and to avoid burns from house-heating radiators, guards or covers can be installed. Clearly, in our patient, the diagnosis of epilepsy leading to burns, was unrecognized, and had triggered unnecessary concern for foul play.

DISCLOSURE

The authors have reported no conflicts of interest.

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